

Evaluation Techniques of Photography in Visual Communications in Iran

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Abstract—Although a picture can be automatically a graphic work, but especially in the field of graphics and images based on the idea of advertising and graphic design will be prepared and photographers to realize the design using his own knowledge and skills to help does. It is evident that knowledge of photography, photographer and designer of the facilities, fields of reaching a higher level of quality offers. At the same time do not have a graphic designer is also skilled photographer, but can execute your idea may delegate to an expert photographer. Using technology and methods in all fields of photography, graphic art may be applicable. But most of its application in Iran, in works such as packaging, posters, Bill Board, advertising, brochures and catalogs are. In this study, we review how the images and techniques in the chart should be used in Iranian graphic photo what impact has left. Using photography techniques and procedures can be designed and helped advance the goals graphic. Technique could not determine the idea. But what is important to think about design and photography and his creativity can flourish as a tool to be effective graphic designer in mind. Computer software to help it's very promotes creativity techniques shall graphic designer but also it is as a tool. Using images in various fields, especially graphic arts and only because it is not being documented, but applications are beautiful. As to his photographic style from today is graphics. Graphic works try to affect impacts on their audience. Hence the photo as an important factor is attention. The other hand saw the man with the extent of forgiving and understanding people's image, instead of using the word to your files, allows large messages and concepts should be sent in the shortest time. Posters, advertisements, brochures, catalog and packaging products very diverse agricultural, industrial and food could not be self-image. Today, the use of graphic images for a big score and the photos to richen the role graphic design plays a major.

Keywords—Photo, Photography Techniques, Contacts, Graphic Designer, Visual Communications, Iran.

I. INTRODUCTION

FROM the early days of photography, photographs were produced based on the few pictures from negatives by photographers; a graphic artist must be able to rational language than any other artist has. The best and easiest way to create speech to the audience is that graphics along with photography make all absence to presence to reach a new idea. In fact photography is a way to achieve a better life so for this reason, perhaps each photo is more efficient for any subject. Use of photo is not practical merely for the documentation, but also for its aesthetic and extensive usage

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to such a degree that today photography is a king of graphics itself based on different photographic styles. The graphic art pieces are trying to affect the mind of audience, so we pay attention to the photos because of its special features.

On the other hand due to the extent of human vision and to visual understanding of people use picture instead of words to transfer messages and broad concepts in the shortest time is very efficient, so picture can improve this basic need in posters, advertisements and brochure.(Fig1-2) Thus photography offering very diverse capabilities and facilities that provide them with conventional methods extremely difficult and sometimes are impossible to learn a world of creativity on the graphic with the help of brief images of photography and composition and combining multiple images, scenes can be exciting and beautiful to watch, witch leaves that viewer with a very strong relationship established make.[1]

Fig. 1.Ad for sneakers

Fig. 2. Poster

Thus photography and graphic help each other to achieve a broad aim and it should be said that using photographs for a graphic artist, is a great advantage. The characteristics and capabilities of photography and images to express ideas with graphic that sometimes is very difficult or not possible for any method to achieve should be considered. It opens a new world of possibilities to the graphic and helps him to realize his goals.

It is evident that knowledge of photography and its features help them to achieve higher quality and provides the context for higher graphic capabilities in implementing ideas, in this field in order to do his ideas technology and various computer software help him. We can say that photography and graphic art as two complementary and specifically for graphics applications are used in the works.(Fig3-4-5)

Fig. 4. Mr. Ghobad Shiva, A retrospective of Paintings & Graphic Designs Mahmud Javadi Pour, 2004

Fig. 3. Maryam Khosravani, 8th Tehran international poster biennale, 2004, proposed.

Fig. 5. Farshid Mesghali Exhibition of 3 continents graphic designers 2004

II. MATERIALS OR METHODS

Based on studies that include a bibliographic works on research articles, books and magazines and a field survey carried out in which related to usage and application of photographic images and graphics techniques used by several photographers and graphic form of questionnaires and statistics and information regarding the amount of use of a graphic image and its various techniques, combining the amount of graphic pictures on the necessity of using a photo as a factor to deliver a message to the audience. How many photos take monthly for graphics work? Use and integration of computer software, how is impressive to this effect from these field studies, use of a questionnaire and in the above study were evaluated

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Type of visual expression and how to use image work will be determined based on content. Using graphic images in the type of work, and in some cases, it is better to use photos.

But it could not be account as a general rule in all type of works or issued to special works. But in cases where their use is essential if you want the audience to believe better and impressed by the photos we use design in order to bring them on for example when you want to have a familiar field for observer that a photo is so important in this case photos are more practical in brochures and catalogs for introducing a product or production process or process of doing using pictures in the press is important because it affects the reader insight on the posters of movie and more different advertising posters and even the photo has a special importance because of communication poster features very high that a major it has attracted for buyers and spectator. Poster should affect the viewers honestly.

Using techniques and photography combining images with other major elements along with a small photo give messages to person and select the color of photos is very important. Due to characteristics of photo can be used as a tool for expressing ideas, graphics along with other existing methods.(Fig. 6)

Fig. 6. Mr. Ghobad Shiva, layout, Iranian costume Magazine, 2005

Graphic artist can help them selves by technical facilities such as lighting issue citations to make clarity and lack of clarity and color distortion in the direction of expression of empowerment photographic techniques have special methods without any mistake, that the technique can not be determinative designer ideas, but his creative thinking and design and photography can be as a tool in order to be effective boom designer mind. Produce any graphic image in a main point technique with a sense of graphic images can reveal itself. Despite the changing trends and to understand all features exaggerated, High contrast to, and not distort the real picture are still distorted from it will be displayed.(Fig7-8)

Fig.7 .Masoud Nejabati, Uniform book, today's literature collection, 2001-2002

Fig. 8. Mr. Ghobad Shiva, book cover, two wings of look I fly, 2002

Briefly it should be said that photography despite any attempts to change its real photo type depends on the subject. Techniques of graphic images have their own unique methods which are often unique and without errors. In other words, they are kind of playing with photography, drawing a lot of pure commercial art designs. Susan Sontag great American intellectual and writer believed that "Pictures are truly catching experience and cameras for conscience, then that desire is seekers, assistance is ideal"[2]. Art alone is real sense of creativity. But the concept of photography in the fabric of real creativity and innovation are interring wind. In oxford dictionary "creative art, especially in the field of visual arts means that were given to intellectual concepts and most valuable aesthetic. [3]This branch of photography is of real importance that was remembered truly and reality of art. This method has its own features that do not match with personal interest of some photographers these days digital photography comes to help the photographer.

Photography is a stable source in nature. How photography has been caused to change and expand of human experience. On the other hand conformity with the reality of photographs cause that has been reliable than any other media. Using photo is the easiest and fastest way for graphics like past. In some years as 1986 the use of photography in graphic reached to a peak while it decreased is some decades. In view of the graphics, image that photo is away to achieve a better life and perhaps this is why photo is more appropriate than other subject. (Fig9-10)

Fig. 9.Reza Abedini, look book, reza abedini book design exhibition,2005.

A poet uses the language and terms of people. Nowadays graphic art is very broad and also is divided into several branches. Book cover design, illustration, layout of magazines and periodicals, advertisements and brochures has their own field. However a picture could be a graphic work but especially in the field of graphics and images, the graphics

will be prepared the photo himself and the photographer will help him by own knowledge and skills.

Photographer and designer agreed will organize the photo with mental images. It is evident that knowledge of photographer and graphics will provide the field for higher quality level. At the same time do not have a graphic designer be also skilled photographer but can give his idea to an expert photographer. With several feedbacks of professional designers in the field of graphic design and advertising can be received. For example in relation to design and advertising poster that aim to promote quality of goods or a recommendation for it.

Fig. 10.Mehdi Mohammadi, 8th Tehran international poster biennial, 2004, proposed.

Most designers prefer to use methods of photography and designs of a packing problem to compete with similar goods are used for more confidence and more forgiving. But the cover of the book is not the case because of the cover design is so important and it is not force to point directly to the content, however this issue is different about other books objects for example, cover of scientific book is required to content directly. In a scientific book a more direct reference to the scientific theme of is required.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aroun.Sharef , *The Art Of Photography*.Iran:Young cinema club pub. of Iran,1993.
- [2] Susan.Sontag, *On Photography*, USA:Published by picador,1977.
- [3] A.S.Hornby.E.V.Gatenby.H.Wakefield,*Oxford(The Advanced Learners Dictionary Of Current English)*, London: Oxford University Press. Ely House, 1963.